

THE ROLE OF DATA MANAGEMENT IN THE NATIONAL TOURISM INFORMATION SYSTEM (SISPARNAS) IN THE SPECIAL REGION OF YOGYAKARTA

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INTRODUCTION

Tourism exercises have advanced quickly, as proven by the expanding number of visitor visits and the advancement of visitor attractions. The improvement of visitor visits is likely to develop since tourism exercises are not just for fun but have ended up being essential for people's life exercises.

Tourism, moreover, incorporates an exceptionally potential and vital part in territorial improvement. It can be a naturally sound improvement approach and a territorial financial balancer. Advancement must be pursued by taking advantage of openings as a source of wage for the local community and territorial wage.

Exercises within the field of tourism are complex exercises covering different divisions and shapes of exercises that have energetic components and are created over time. Based on this, tourism improvement will experience a process of physical and social alteration. The method of alteration proceeds in conjunction with the advancement of the framework and other offices. In other words, tourism arranging starts with the improvement of territorial tourism, which incorporates the physical advancement of advanced visitor attractions.

The development of regional tourism destinations is a complex activity that improves both the quantity and quality of tourism destination services for tourists. In its implementation, adequate data and information related to tourism conditions in the area are needed as a basis for policymaking. In addition, the availability of regional tourism data and information will make it easier for tourists to access information to determine their travel plans.

There are two pivotal issues in giving a territorial tourism database:

We are collecting and overseeing territorial tourism information. Information collection is related to information completeness, whereas information administration is related to information introduction and capacity. This movement was started to oversee the territorial tourism database carefully and coordinate it from the area, city, common, and national levels. With total territorial tourism information digitized from the locales to the center, it is trusted that Indonesia is prepared to enter the change of the advanced tourism industry.

Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism Article 32 states that the Government and Territorial Governments ensure the accessibility and dispersal of data to the open to advantage tourism improvement. In Government Control Number 50 of 2011 concerning the National Tourism Improvement Ace Arrange for 2010-2025, Article 25 states that the arrangement course of the Improvement of Open Foundation, Open

Offices, and Tourism Offices incorporates advancement, advancement, and control of Open Framework, Open Offices, and Tourism Offices in supporting the spearheading, development, making strides quality, revitalization and competitiveness of DPN (National Tourism Goal). Tourism offices can incorporate tourism data and benefit offices, migration benefit offices, tourism data centers, and e-tourism booths.

In the context of the Tourism Destination Governance Development Program, the Deputy for Destination Development and Infrastructure / Directorate of Tourism Destination Governance of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy / Indonesian Tourism and Creative Economy Agency Deconcentration Activities for the Development of the National Tourism Information System (SISPARNAS). The DIY Tourism Office also supports by carrying out these activities through the Deconcentration Fund.

LITERATURE

Tourism

Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism suggests tourism could be a travel action carried out by an individual or a bunch of individuals by going to a particular place for recreational purposes, individual advancement, or learning the uniqueness of the fascination of tourist attractions visited briefly. In the interim, the definition of tourism may be an assortment of tourism exercises upheld by different offices and administrations given by the community, business visionaries, government, and nearby governments. Marpaung in Usman Chamdani (2019: 6) characterizes tourism as a travel movement by individuals going to certain places for recreational purposes, self-development, or learning about traveler attractions. Kagungan and Meutia (2018) state that the improvement of tourism within the period of digitalization, if created successfully, will have an advantageous effect and benefit neighborhood communities, particularly. It can be concluded that tourism has meaning as a frame of riches, potential, and fascination claimed by Lampung Area. It is realized through traveler attractions, social celebrations, culinary characteristics, etc. At that point, it is created and advanced through a website-based administration data framework so that the open can effectively see and acknowledge data as a medium that appears the side of excellence, uniqueness, history, and celebrations and celebrations as characteristics.

Website

Concurring to Rahmat Hidayat, cited from Nurmi (2013), an online site or location can be deciphered as a collection of pages utilized to show content data, still pictures or movement, liveliness, sound, and or a combination of all of them, both inactive and energetic that frame an arrangement of interconnected buildings, each of which is associated by a organize of pages. Ali Zaki in Harminingtyas (2014), websites have different capacities, depending on the reason and sort of site being built. Still, they can work as a medium for advancement, communication/information, and instruction. It can be concluded that this site comforts tourists about tourism and can offer assistance within the wide spread of data without knowing time and space limits. The tourism office site is exceptionally steady in creating tourism capacities in cities/districts. The assignments of tourism advancement incorporate the improvement of traveler objects and attractions, the enhancement of advancement and promotion, and (3) the change of tourism instruction and preparation.

Tourism Framework Agreeing to Leiper (1990:22-32) and Cooper et al. (1999:4-8), the components of a basic tourism framework include a visitor region/country of the root, a traveler goal area/country, and travel put and a generator that inverts the method as there are five fundamental components, to be specific traveler-generating locale, leaving traveler, travel course locale, traveler goal locale, and returning traveler. Be that as it may, the five center components concern three primary things: the visitor component, the three topographical components (a combination of travel generators, travel courses, and traveler goals), and the tourism industry component.

Figure 1: Tourism System Model According to Leiper

Tourist element

Tourists are actors in the tourism system. Tourism is ultimately a humanist, fun, and unforgettable experience that is one of the most important parts of the perpetrator's life.

Geographical elements

It concerns three components, specifically: (1) traveler-generating locale, (2) traveler-goal locale, and (3) travel course locale. Traveler-generating districts are the root and showcase of tourism where imminent visitors look for data around their visitor goals, make travel booking exchanges, and where the visitors withdraw for visitor goals.

The visitor goal locale may be a traveler's travel goal. As a traveler's goal, the impact of tourism will be felt foremost by other districts. In Pith, visitor goals are one-of-a-kind regions that vary from diverse locales, counting locales or nations of beginning-of-seekers. These uniqueness and contrasts can be in culture, history, nature, etc. This uniqueness is usually called a traveler's fascination. Typically, the driving vitality for the complete tourism framework comes about within the request for visitor travel for territorial travelers. The tourism system's most sensational results happen in this visitor goal range.

Travel course locales speak to not only a temporary time and place for a visitor trip to reach the driving goal but also its opportunity to become an en-route visitor goal. In this concept, there's continuously an interim of time and place for a traveler's trip when a traveler feels they have cleared out their place of roots but have not arrived at the place they chose to visit as a traveler's goal.

Elements of the tourism industry

The final component within the Leiper demonstration is the tourism industry, which we will envision as the commerce and organizational regions involved in creating tourism products. For illustration, travel specialists and visit administrators are found within the traveler-generating region category. Traveler attractions and the hotel/restaurant industry are in the goal locale. The transportation division is mostly found within the territorial travel course.

Each component of the Leiper tourism framework is interatomic, not in terms of tourism items but, moreover, in terms of exchanges, impacts, and different settings and results in which tourism is found.

The main advantage of the Leiper tourism system model is its simplicity and ease of application, which provides a way of thinking about tourism; the Leiper model can also be sorted to simplify the analysis so that it is more detailed and specific. According to Cooper et al. (1999: 6), the advantages of using the Leiper tourism system model approach include:

- 1) Its ability to integrate an interdisciplinary approach in the study of tourism is due to the model's being not rooted in a single subject and specific discipline but providing a framework that allows a particular disciplinary approach to be applied.
- 2) The model can be applied at various scales and levels, from a local resort to a national tourism industry.
- 3) The model is very flexible and allows it to represent various forms of tourism by sorting and analyzing the main elements of these forms of tourism.
- 4) The model can describe important principles in tourism studies, where all elements of tourism are interconnected and interact. In some approaches, the components of tourism are separated and analyzed separately, but in reality, they are all interrelated, which provides a comprehensive understanding of the existence of tourism.

Mathieson and Wall (1982) also describe the tourism system, which shows that it consists of three elements: (1) the dynamic element, the tourist journey; (2) the static element, the presence in the destination; and (3) the consequential element, the various impacts that arise, such as economic, socio-cultural, and environmental impacts.

Process and Morrison (1985, CF. Fennel, 1999) moreover created a demonstration of the tourism framework, which comprises of the taking after four primary components:

- 1) Advertise (coming to the commercial center),
- 2) Travel (the buying of travel items)
- 3) Goal (the shape of travel request) dan
- 4) Promoting (the offering of travel)
- 5) *Marketing (the selling of travel)*

Figure 2: The Tourism System Model According to Mill and Morrison

Poon (1993) sees the tourism system from a different perspective, namely emphasizing more on the aspect of tourism marketing. It is said that the tourism system consists of (1) a sub-system of production, (2) a sub-system of delivery, (3) a sub-system of management, and (4) a sub-system of distribution and sales.

Tourism is a very complex activity that involves many related elements, where the effectiveness of the linkage will affect the performance of tourism development. Therefore, in its development, tourism must be seen as a system of linkages between demand and supply factors. The request figure comprises the household and outside traveler markets, which require different administrations. In contrast, visitors outside the environment where they live are given by the government and the private segment within the put gone by. Arrangement components incorporate objects and attractions, visitor exercises, housing, and other visitor offices and administrations. What is implied by the tourism regulation system, in this case, maybe an expressive clarification of how the division of obligations is between different interested parties: the government (open division), the private division (counting components of the tourism industry as proposed by Leiper), and the community in realizing the objectives of tourism advancement. This regulation framework verifiably contains the meaning that the parts of the different parties back each other to form collaboration, which no one party can realize without the contribution/participation of other parties.

METHOD

This ponder employs expressive investigation with a quantitative approach. A quantitative graphic approach is carried out to record, portray, analyze, and decipher the part of information administration of the National Tourism Data Framework (SISPARNAS) related to the part of partners in overseeing tourism within the Uncommon Locale of Yogyakarta. The area of this think about as it were covers the

Uncommon Locale of Yogyakarta, which comprises five areas, specifically Sleman Rule, Bantul Rule, Gunungkidul Rule, Kulonprogo Rule, and Yogyakarta City. Investigate exercises incorporate in-depth interviews and center Gather Discourses (FGD)—documentation and Strategies for Information Triangulation Legitimacy.

DISCUSSION

National Tourism Data Framework (SISPARNAS)

SISPARNAS could be an information stage for the presence of traveler attractions, attractions and the accessibility of supporting foundations from all districts in Indonesia, utilizing enormous information innovation advancements and versatile approaches to outline, both in terms of potential and fortifying the tourism segment, creating data on tourism pointers to bolster policy-making as benefit offices given for tourism performing artists and neighborhood governments in understanding with the order of the Law No.10 of 2009 concerning tourism.

Within the setting of the usage of the Deconcentration of the Appointee for Goal and Framework Improvement for the 2022 Financial Year and the execution of the order of Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism, to expressly guarantee the accessibility and spread of data to the public for the good thing about tourism improvement, the DIY Tourism Office carried out Tourism Data Framework Improvement exercises.

SISPARNAS could be a national tourism information and data center. Information sources are input autonomously by goal supervisors, the tourism industry, and the Common Rule, and City Tourism Workplaces. The information handle is created with the rule of information centralization or tourism information. Provincial/Regency and City Tourism Workplaces that have dashboards and collection disobedient.

Figure 3: Sisparnas Web

Figure 4: National (SISPARNAS) in 2022.

The implementation of the development of the National Tourism Information System (SISPARNAS) includes the following:

Figure 5: Timeline Activity SISPARNAS

Technical Guidance

Technical Guidance for Filling in the National Tourism Information System (SISPARNAS) was held on August 8, 2022, at The Alana Yogyakarta Hotel and Convention Center. Technical guidance materials include:

- 1) Technical Instructions for the Implementation of Deconcentration of the Development of the National Tourism Information System (SISPARNAS) FY 2022 by the Resource Person of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy of the Republic of Indonesia, Mrs. Nur Azizah Irawati, S.T. Sub-Coordinator of Infrastructure, Accessibility, Connectivity, Amenities/Facilitation, Digitalization.

- 2) Instructions for the Use of the National Tourism Information System (SISPARNAS) by the Resource Person of the Sisparnas Consulting Team of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy of the Republic of Indonesia, Mr. Toni Bagus Murdjayanto
- 3) Sustainable Tourism Information by Resource Person Ike Janita Dewi SE, MBA, Ph.D (Lecturer at Sanata Dharma University)
- 4) Processing of Tourism Statistics Data by Provincial BPS Resource Persons
- 5) D.I. Yogyakarta Mr. Amirudin (Associate Statistician, Coordinator of Distribution Statistics Function)

Execution of Information Collection through Field Studies and SISPARNAS Information Filling

Information collection exercises through field studies were carried out from Admirable 16 to 2019. November 2022 started with the issuance of the Proclaim of the Head of the DIY Tourism Office Number 188/06040 dated Admirable 16, 2022, concerning the Foundation of Facilitators of Surveyors and Surveyors for Advancement Exercises. SISPARNAS for Monetary Year 2022, which included the composition of the workforce and the SISPARNAS Overview and Information Collection Exercises, was carried out from Admirable 16 to November 16, 2022.

The recap of the Supervisor Surveyor Frame Information that has been collected incorporates:

Yogyakarta.

- 1) Museums: General Sudirman Museum, Vredeborg Fort Museum, Yogyakarta Palace, Bebadan Museum Puro Pakualam, Gembira Loka Zoo, Dr. Yap Prawirohusodo Museum, TNI AD Dharma Wiratama Central Museum, Prince Diponegoro Monument Museum, Yogyakarta Smart Park, Yogyakarta Struggle Museum, Kotagede Museum: Intro Living Museum, Sandi Museum, Sonobudoyo Museum, Taman Sari Tour, Banana Nufah Plasma Garden, Lepen Dam, Pagelaran Museum, Urban Tourism Dipo, Tomb of King Kotagede, Kirti Griya Aerospace Museum, Rejowinangun Tourism Village.
- 2) Hotels: Hotel Tara, Hotel Ibis, Hotel Forris, Hotel Horison, Hotel Grand Kangen, Hotel Neo, Hotel 101, Hotel Pyness, Hotel Alamanda, Hotel Patra, Hotel Villas, Hotel Gallery, Hotel Swiss Bell, Hotel Sagan, Hotel Pop, Hotel Harper, Hotel Grand Zurich, Hotel Fave, Hotel De Laxton, Hotel Royal Dharmo, Hotel Kotta Go Hotel, Hotel Malioboro Inn, Hotel Grand Kangen.
- 3) Food and Beverages: Chef Joni, Gudeg Rahayu Sagan, Ayam taliwang Papin, Sekar Kedhaton Restaurant, Nanamia Pizzeria, Chef Joni, Silol Kopi and Eatery, Raminten's Kitchen, Recheese, The House of Raminten, Yamie Singkawang, Roemi (RumahMirolta), Waroeng Klangeran, Bale Timoho Resto, Mamahke Jogja, Tojoyo Rm. Padang Duta Minang, Spoon Bebek, Dapur Manado, Oase Café & Resto, Terra Café, Ayam Taliwang Papin, Banh Mi Pho Min'bar, Ayam Bakar Mas Yogi, Rm. Padang Murah Jaya, Lesehan Aneka, Fave Hotel (Resto), Grand Kangen (Resto), R&B Grill, Dapur Manado, Indonesia Hotel Resto.

Sleman

- 1) Tourist Destinations: Tebing Beksi, Suraloka, Satoloka, Mount Merapi Museum, Merapi Landmark, Bumi Merapi. Blue Lagoon, Kaliurang Park, Omah Salak, Jogja Kembali Museum, UPN Museum, Gamplong Nature Studio, Exotarium, Jamu Godhog, Sindu Kusuma Edupark, Prambanan Temple, Suraloka, UPN Geo Mineral Museum, Education Museum, Jogja Kembali Museum, Sentalu Ulen Museum
- 2) Hotels: Hotel Porta, The Manohara, Sumber Watu Heritage, Bueno Colombo, Inside Hotel, Santoria Hotel, Jayakarta Hotel, Yellow Star Hotel, Grand Mercure Utara Hotel, Grand Serella Hotel, Hotel Sahid Rich, The Atrium Hotel And Resort, Seraton Hotel, Dafam Hotel, Grand Keisha, Lavayete, Hotel, Brother In Hotel, Platinum hotel
- 3) Food and Beverage Services: Jadah Mbak Carik, Obelix Hills, Soto Bathok Sambisari, Mang Engking Resto, Iwak Kalen Resto, Sendang Ayu Resto, Ayam Goreng Kalasan Candi Sari, Kopi Merapi, Ambayagiri Resto, Ayam Mbah Wanto., Mbok Berek, Pring Sewu, West Lake, Puri Mataram, Floating Resto, Jejamuran, Pelem Golek, Sasanti, Bale Woku. SDPC Bu Wiryo, Tengkleng Gajah, Klothok Coffee.

Bantul

1. Tourist Destinations: Grand Puri Water Park, History of JavaMuseum, Gumuk Pasir Museum., Chocolate Monggo Museum, Tirta Taman Sari, Becici Peak, Thousand Stone Tourism, Pengger Pinus, Bukit Lintang Sewu, Pinus Sari, Cerme Cave, Selarong Cave, Parangtritis Beach, Kids Fun, Balong Park, Depok Beach, New Beach, Samas Beach, Pandansari Beach, Cemara Cave Beach, Tubing Karst, Fruit Garden, Mangunan, Tino Sidin Park Museum, Selopamioro Adventure Park.
2. Hotels: Hotel Gandung, Hotel Gemah Ripah, Hotel Wijaya Imperial, Hotel Candi Tirto Raharjo, Bukit Hijau Hotel, Hotel Gaharu, Hotel Adinda, Bluesteps, Tembi Rumah Budaya, D'Omah Hotel, Ros-In Hotel, Grand Rohan Jogja, Joglo Mandapa Boutique Hotel, Villa Kayu and Bungalow, Rajaklana Resort and SPA, Griya Mataram.,
3. Food and Beverage Services: Bukit Indah Resto, SKP Sido Kumpul, Sate Pak Pong, Restaurant, Kedung Bumbu, Gudeg Bu Tjitro 1925 Janti, Omah Dhuwur Restaurant, Ayam Goreng Mbah, Cemplung, RM. Giri Tirto H. Atemo, RM. Mataram Indah, RM. Mrs. Suharti, Pondok Bakaran, Waroeng Omah Sawah, RM. Parangtritis, Numani Resto, Gubug Makan Mang Engking, Kopi Nuri ISI

Gunungkidul Regency

- 1) Tourist Destinations: Baron Beach, Ngobaran Beach, Ngrenahan Beach, Kukup Beach, Sanglen Beach, Ngingrong Cave, Tahura Bunder, Wediombo Beach, Kalisuci Cave Tubing, Jonge Lake, Watu Giring, Glass Terrace, Segoro Peak, Watugupit Paragliding, Sri Waterfall, ethuk, Water Byur, Pulutan Village Valley, Pulang Syawal, Watu Gendong Tourism, Tanding Cave, Wonosadi Customary Forest, Watu Payung Derivative Geoforest
- 2) Hotel : Homestay Joglo Jawa, Griya Limasan Hotel, Baronsari, Jaya Motel, Orchid In, Hotel Santika Gunungkidul, Hotel Calida, Hotel DeaLokha, Alzara Hotel

Syariah, The Mulyo, Giri Wanara Glamping Resort. Kampoeng Baron Guesthouse, Baron Lighthouse Cottage & Eatery, Acala Ayu Homestay, Sidodadi Inn, Kukup Indah Inn, Inessya Resort, Pins Homestay, Walet Guesthouse, Cemara Udang Inn, Royal Joglo, Joglo Wediombo, Queen of The South Resort, Villa Tirtasari, Wisma Joglo

- 3) Jasa Makanan dan Minuman : Sere Ratu Resto, Daharan Den Ayu, Nasi Merah Pari Gogo, Pondok Makan Sekar Kusuma, Layah Kembar, Pondok Ikan Bakar Bu Shintia, Ayam Goreng Pak Parman, Rumah Makan KelapaGading, Warung Makan Ayam Goreng & Bakar BuSabar, Moro Joglo, The Manglung, Omahena, Warung Simbok, Ayam Goreng Kondang Rasa, Bebek Goreng pak Koes, Ayam Taliwang Mbok Karni, Rumah Makan Bu Tiwi Tan Tlogo, Omah Kampoeng Kuliner, Griyo Dhahar Mbak Bagong, Sego Abang Gunungkidul, Kampoeng Ngingrong, Rumah Makan Seger Waras, Wulenpari, South Shore, Sambel Mentah P-3 Joyo, Rumah Makan Sido Dadi, Gaung Resto, 19. Rumah Makan Padang Tuah Saiyo Baleharjo

Kulonprogo Regency

- 1) Tourist Destinations: Sendangsono, Kleco Peak, Glagah Beach, Trisik Beach, Congot Beach, Suroloyo Peak, Blue River, Sermo Reservoir, Kadilangu Beach Mangrove Forest, Pule Payung, Dolan Deso Boro, Kemadon Peak, Kedung Pedhut, Kembangsoka, Mudal River Ecotourism, Sky Swing, Kebon Cave, Bidara Beach, Mlarangan Asri Beach, Nglinggo Tea Garden, Kiskendo Cave, Rajendra Farm, Widosari Peak,
- 2) Usaha Jasa Makanan dan Minuman: Pawon Gunung Kiskendo, Kedai Kopi Pari, Dapoer Khayangan, Omah Tabon, Geblek Menoreh View, Mahaloka, Geblek Pari, Terraloka, Marron Café, Kopi Ingkar Janji, Dadap Sumilir, Kopi Ampirano, Kopi Klotok Menoreh, Gubuk Makan Iwak Kalen, Iwak Progo, Pari Klegung, Kripala, Teras Menoreh, La Barca, Puncak Saka, Omah Cantrik, De Atemos, Terraskota, Bu Hartin, Resto Bukit Cubung, Kopi Jolotundo, Gili Bistro,
- 3) Accommodation Services Business: Hotel Rompok Jogja, Hotel Anugrah, Hotel Lumintu, Hotel Cordia, Hotel Hapsari, Hotel King, Hotel Primitif, Guest House Primitif, Hotel Grand Dafam, Hotel Kusuma, Hotel New Citra.

Figure 6: Destination Capacity

Figure 7: Competitiveness Index

Figures 6 and 7 show the goal capacity and competitiveness record on the SISPARNAS site for each Rule / Region within the Extraordinary Locale of Yogyakarta. The following could be a table of the results of the month-to-month information collection recap by the surveyor group related to information on nourishment and refreshment administrations, inn settlement administrations, and visitor attractions per month for three months in Regencies and Cities.

SISPARNAS Data Filling

The execution of the Center Gather Talk (FGD) on the information introduction of the National Tourism Data Framework (SISPARNAS) was held on November 10, 2022, at The Alana Yogyakarta Inn and Tradition Center. The Rundown Center Gather Discourse (FGD)

Figure 8: Sustainable Tourism

Figure 9: Economics

The Center Bunch Talk (FGD) was opened by Mr. Kurniawan, S.Sos, SE. Akt, MEc.Dev.Head of Goal Advancement speaking to the Head of the DIY Tourism Office was gone to by Scholastics, Surveyor Facilitators, Scholarly Surveyors, Surveyors of Rule and City Tourism Workplaces, Echelon III and Echelon IV Authorities of the DIY Tourism Office, Administration of the Indonesian Inn and Eatery Affiliation (PHRI) DPD Yogyakarta, Administration of the Indonesian Tourism Affiliation (HPI), as well as PPKom and State Budget Supervisors of the DIY Tourism Office by showing competent asset people related to Improvement National Tourism Data Framework (SISPARNAS). This FGD movement was carried out by marking the minutes of executing the deconcentration of SISPARNAS improvement of the D.I. Yogyakarta Area.

Figure 10: Accommodation

Figure 11: Food and Beverage

Figure 12: Tourist Attractions

Figure 13: Tourist Visits

Yogyakarta City

Data Survey	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Total
Food and Beverage Services	0	25	3	28
Hotel Services	0	19	3	22
Tourism Attractions	0	14	7	21
Total	0	58	13	71

Sleman Regency

Data Survey	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Total
Food and beverage services	10	4	8	22
Hotel accommodation services	4	12	7	23
Tourist attractions	6	9	6	21
Total	20	40	6	66

Gunungkidul Regency

Data Survey	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Total
Food and Beverage Services	10	15	3	28
Hotel Services	9	2	14	25
Tourism Attractions	8	5	12	25
Total	27	22	29	78

Bantul Regency

Database	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Total
Food and Beverage Services	15	14	1	30
Hotel Accommodation Services	15	9	1	25
Tourist Attractions	5	12	8	25
Total	35	35	10	80

Kulonprogo Regency

Data Survey	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Total
Food and Beverage Services	0	20	7	27
Hotel Services	0	0	11	11
Tourism Attractions	21	0	2	23
Total	21	20	20	61

CONCLUSION

Implementing the National Tourism Information System Development (SISPARNAS) activities for the 2022 Fiscal Year in Yogyakarta has been carried out smoothly. It is hoped that the implementation of the National Tourism Information System Development Activity (SISPARNAS) will continue in the coming years so that it will continue to be sustainable in the context of compiling data and information on tourism and regional creative economy in encouraging the development of tourism in the region, especially in Yogyakarta. In addition, it is expected to be able to synchronize manual form items with digital form items.

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